

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF THE PROCESS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS

Akhmedova Mushtariybonu Makhmudjonovna

1st year student of primary education, Faculty of Pedagogy

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

Scientific supervisor: Akhmedova Matluba Akmalovna

Acting associate professor, Head of the Department of Russian

Language

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the ways and possibilities of improving the socio-psychological principles of inclusive education process in schools were considered.

The science of pedagogy is defined as the science of the laws of education and upbringing of children and adults. Its main task is to determine the laws in the field of upbringing, education, training, education and management of educational systems. is to provide equality of opportunities, to have a friendly relationship with them and to ease their social adaptation to society, to create the necessary pedagogical, psychological and correctional conditions for the education of students.

If all ordinary children attend comprehensive schools, children with special needs should also be included. It is important that inclusive education is implemented starting from the family and preschool educational institutions. This will help children to communicate with others, meet the demands of the social environment and, at the same time, to acquire the skills to meet their daily and household needs early, to adapt to life, to learn lessons on time along with their peers in general education schools, and to acquire the ability to approach tasks responsibly. Inclusive education in comprehensive schools is an education system that is flexible, individualized and provides equal rights and opportunities to all children, for children with special needs or for other reasons. In addition, inclusive education is an education that implies treating all children equally, regardless of their nationality, race, body color, social origin, material and spiritual status, the role of their family in society, physical or developmental disabilities, and supporting all their opportunities.

Inclusive school - schools with inclusive education protect children's individual rights to education. It is a school where students are diverse, healthy and with mild disabilities, and all of them have equal opportunities to realize their potential.

The program of inclusive education was adopted at the World Conference on Special Needs Education in Salamanca, Spain, with the participation of representatives of 92 countries and 25 international organizations. It adopted the "Salamanca Declaration" on the principles and reforms of special education for all, recognizing that it is necessary and necessary to educate children, youth and adults with special needs within the framework of the regular education system. It urged everyone: "We invite and appeal to all countries: accept the principle of inclusive education as a law or reform". Its purpose is to inform states, international organizations, national aid associations, non-governmental organizations and other departments about the reforms and activities of the statement on the practice, reform and principles of special needs education. The program was developed by the United Nations and on the basis of the experiences of the countries participating in the conference, as well as the manuscripts, recommendations and solutions of various issues published by other international organizations, especially the standard rules for stabilizing the opportunities of disabled persons.

The right to education for every child was adopted in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and reaffirmed in the Universal Declaration of Education for All. Every person with a disability has the right to express their wishes based on their acquired education, if requested. Parents have the right to get advice on choosing the form of education that suits their children's wishes, situation, and needs. Inclusive education is an educational system that is individualized and adapted to the needs of children and young people with special needs. These works are carried out in ordinary, moderately developed children's educational institutions. To do this, it is necessary to approach each child individually, based on their disability, and create comfortable conditions for them. Children with special needs attend a public kindergarten or school that is convenient for them. The main work there is done by the educator or class leader. The process of inclusive education in comprehensive schools has its own complexities, and serious demands are placed on officials and teachers working in this field. In this type of education, the head of the class, subject teachers, tutors, masters of professional skills perform support services. The difference between healthy children and children who need special attention is due to the fact that they do not fit in with their peers due to their limited physical abilities, shyness, shyness or humiliation, and some of them become stubborn and capricious due to excessive care in the family.

Each inclusive education has a specially trained (resource) pedagogue. The importance of the prestige of the institutions of inclusive education depends on the teachers who have this special training. Because he advises and helps the group educator, provides special teaching equipment and supplies, conducts explanatory work with parents and teachers, makes changes to the lesson schedule and program, if necessary, and justifies them. It also increases the qualifications of teachers working in this direction, enriches knowledge, organizes health services, and creates a comfortable psychological environment. This program of educational activities depends on a number of special, regional and level factors. They serve to prepare society's perspective, needs, resource requirements, and specialists.

Experiments show that various problems encountered in achieving high educational success in organizing the education of children involved in inclusive education and needing special attention are related to the extent to which the individual mental experiences of children are taken into account. In order to gain self-confidence and prevent disappointment in children who need special attention, the teacher's activities should be carried out in cooperation with parents. In inclusive education, basic teacher training and improving the basic conditions necessary to ensure that schools work for all require teachers to instill a sense of responsibility in classrooms for all children. Teaching students with special needs according to their interests, knowledge and abilities is a common activity in the classroom (Figure 1).

Fig 1. Inclusive education activity program.

Regional (national) level activity departments of the inclusive education activity program

Guidelines for regional and international activities

Resource (resource) requirements

Fronts with high status

Society's interests

External support services

Recruitment and training of teachers

New Perspectives in Special Needs Education

School factors

Reform and organization

Inclusive education based on children with special needs also benefits society. This, in turn, is the first step towards integration, placing a child with a physical or mental disability in a regular kindergarten or school. In an integrated society, everyone has equal rights, it is a whole society.

Through inclusive education, society becomes an integrated society and promotes effective pedagogic principles that benefit all children. It is accepted that different types of people are normal, and based on the nature and stages of the learning process, the child should be adapted to the needs of the child, not to the requirements of the process.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" lists the insufficient development of inclusive education programs in the public education system, problems in ensuring special training of teachers on inclusive education in the programs of higher educational institutions of our country. To solve these problems by organizing an inclusive education system for teaching children with disabilities, to provide general education institutions with special equipment (elevating device, ramp, handrail, etc.), as well as relevant personnel (pedagogue-defectologist, specialists in psycho-pedagogical observation of children), The priority direction of the development of the public education system is to carry out explanatory work among the public about the right to education of children with disabilities, the essence of inclusive education.

In the Law "On Education" adopted on September 23, 2020, inclusive education is recognized as one of the forms of education, and children with physical, mental, sensory or mental disabilities, as well as children who need long-term treatment, are enrolled in state specialized educational institutions, general secondary and the right to receive education in an inclusive form or in home conditions is guaranteed in secondary special education organizations.

With the Presidential Decree of October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs", gradual introduction of inclusive general education until 2025, creating a barrier-free environment for children with disabilities to come to schools, newly built Necessary tasks were defined in terms of building schools with favorable conditions for the disabled, training pedagogues, and improving the educational base. In addition, the decision approved the "Concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2025" in order to organize an inclusive education system for teaching children with special educational needs, to guarantee and ensure their right to education. Training, retraining and professional development of pedagogues for the inclusive education system, development and implementation of mechanisms aimed at preventing discrimination of children with special educational needs, cruel or degrading treatment towards them, educational institutions for students involved in inclusive education provision of specially equipped computer equipment, interactive whiteboard, hearing devices and other equipment was defined as the priority tasks of the Concept. On October 12 of this year, Cabinet of Ministers decision No. 638 "On approval of normative legal documents on education of children with special educational needs" was adopted in connection with the implementation of these tasks. The decision "On the procedure for organizing inclusive education in general secondary education organizations" was approved.

According to this regulation, inclusive education is education that provides equal opportunities for all learners to receive education in educational institutions, taking into account the diversity of individual educational needs and individual capabilities. The purpose and tasks of inclusive education, the organization of the educational process in inclusive education classes and elementary correctional classes, the admission of students to these classes, the activities of

pedagogic staff and the procedure for cooperation with parents are regulated by this regulatory legal document.

In particular, students are admitted to the first grade of the school's inclusive education classes and elementary correctional classes in the year they turn seven years old. According to the conclusion of the Psychological-Medical-Pedagogical Commission established under the Regional Department of Public Education, the admission and dismissal of students to these classes is carried out with the consent of parents or their substitutes. Also, the total number of students in inclusive education classes should not exceed 30. The number of students with special educational needs studying on the basis of special (corrective) programs should not exceed 3 students in these classes. Only students with the same medical diagnosis are admitted to inclusive education classes and primary correctional classes.

In conclusion, it can be said that the improvement of the education sector, in particular the legislation on inclusive education, and the implementation of gradual reforms in this regard will provide equal rights and opportunities to children with special educational needs and disabilities in our country to receive education in the same conditions as healthy children.

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